

1 **Holm oak decline and mortality exacerbates drought effects on soil biogeochemical**
2 **cycles, rates of carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) mineralization and abundances of key**
3 **functional groups on a climatic gradient**

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23 *ectomycorrhizal (ECM), cascading effects.*

24

25 **Summary**

26

27 The extent to which the increasingly frequent episodes of drought-induced tree decline
28 and mortality could alter key soil biogeochemical cycles is still unclear. This aspect is
29 particularly relevant, since forested ecosystems serve as important long-term sinks for
30 carbon (C) and essential nutrients (e.g. nitrogen and phosphorus). In order to fill in this
31 knowledge gap, we conducted a study on 13 study sites distributed across the Spanish
32 Iberian Peninsula where the dominant tree species was the Mediterranean evergreen
33 Holm oak (*Quercus ilex* L. subsp. *ballota* [Desf.] Samp), a species that has shown
34 important drought-induced crown defoliation and mortality rates during recent decades.
35 Our study covered different climatic, soil, land-use type (forests, dehesas, and open
36 woodlands), and crown defoliation (healthy, affected, and dead Holm oaks) gradients that
37 might characterize this species distribution within the Spanish Iberian Peninsula.
38 Specifically, the soil C and nutrient content (nitrogen, N; phosphorus, P; magnesium,
39 Mg), its functional parameters (heterotrophic respiration (R_H), N ammonification (R_{amm}
40 and N nitrification (R_{nit})), and relative abundances of key microbial soil functional groups
41 (Nitrifiers and ectomycorrhiza) were studied here. Our results showed that besides the
42 potential effects associated with the climatic gradient considered for this study, Holm
43 oaks mortality resulted in soil stoichiometric imbalances, triggered by net losses of
44 essential oligonutrients (e.g. Mg), and accumulation of very mobile forms of nitrogen
45 ($NO_3^- - N$) and phosphorus (Av P). Changes in the abundance of key microbial soil
46 functional groups (Nitrifiers and ectomycorrhiza) co-occurred with observed N and P
47 imbalances. Therefore, we conclude that the potential vulnerability of soil C and nutrient
48 stocks to ongoing changes in climate may strongly depend on tree vulnerability to climate
49 change, its effect on soil-plant relationships, and how this may impact the ecology and
50 functioning of key soil functional groups and key metabolic pathways.

51 **1. Introduction**

52 It is expected that increases in the severity of the drought events associated with climate
53 change will have an enormous impact over soil biogeochemical cycling (Schlesinger et
54 al. 2016). This is, as many studies have shown, because soil biota (e.g. Curiel Yuste et
55 al., 2014; Kandeler et al., 2015; Valencia et al., 2018; Moreno-Jiménez et al., 2019) and
56 its functioning (e.g. Curiel Yuste et al., 2007; Chen et al., 2011; Moyano et al., 2012; Ye
57 et al., 2019) are extremely sensitive to changes in water availability, which subsequently
58 impacts the cycling of C and nutrients in soils (e.g. Sardans and Peñuelas, 2005; Larsen
59 et al., 2011; Xu et al., 2016; Curiel Yuste et al., 2017). In the particular case of
60 Mediterranean ecosystems, where soil moisture plays a critical role in plant growth and
61 soil activity (Vilà and Sardans, 1999; Sardans and Peñuelas, 2005; Casals et al., 2009),
62 both the duration of drought events (e.g., Ma et al. (2012); Vargas et al. (2018) and the
63 cycles of drying and rewetting to which soils are submitted (e.g., Barnard et al. (2013);
64 Rodríguez et al. (2019) have been identified as drivers of change in rates of soil
65 biogeochemical cycling.

66

67 Still, so far, studies and models have generally omitted other potentially important
68 impacts of the observed increases in the frequency and intensity of drought on the soil
69 ecosystem. Specifically, the extent to which events of tree decline and mortality
70 associated with drought (Allen et al., 2010; Allen et al., 2015; Hartmann et al., 2018), in
71 some cases coinciding with pathogen outbreaks (Edburg et al., 2012; Corcobado et al.,
72 2014), are affecting the functioning of the soil ecosystem are still unknown (Anderegg et
73 al., 2012; McDowell et al., 2018). This knowledge gap is of particular relevance since
74 tree decline and mortality has become a worrisome phenomenon now affecting ecosystem
75 forests all over the world (Allen et al., 2010; Allen et al., 2015; Hartmann et al., 2018)

76 and climate change models forecast more frequent and intense drought events (IPCC,
77 2014; Mariotti et al., 2015), which will probably determine more tree decline and
78 mortality events. However, there are still many uncertainties about the extent to which
79 tree mortality could affect the functioning of soils and their ability to sequester C and
80 nutrients (Schlesinger et al. 2016). Since soil microbial communities and nutrient cycling
81 related functions are very sensitive to changes in microclimatic conditions (Sardans and
82 Peñuelas, 2005; Sardans et al., 2006; Curiel Yuste et al., 2007; Curiel Yuste et al., 2017)
83 alterations associated with crown defoliation of the soil microclimatic conditions due to
84 decreases in transpiration or canopy interception of precipitation and solar radiation
85 (Anderegg et al., 2012) may severely affect soil functioning and soil biogeochemical
86 cycling. Furthermore, modification of the belowground carbon (C) flow, as a result of the
87 interruption of exudation (Högberg et al., 2001) and/or the increased input of litterfall and
88 dead wood (Curiel Yuste et al., 2019), may also alter nutrient and C cycling (Avila et al.,
89 2016; Rodríguez et al., 2017; Flores-Rentería et al., 2018) and the composition of key
90 microbial soil functional groups (Curiel Yuste et al., 2012; Lloret et al., 2015). The
91 cycling of nitrogen (N) in soil, which is particularly sensitivity to changes in soil moisture
92 (Chen et al., 2011; Griffin et al., 2011; Lupon et al., 2015; Xu et al., 2016), might be also
93 sensitive to the microclimatic alterations associated with tree decline. For instance,
94 Rodríguez et al. (2017), found a significant increase in N mineralization due to drought-
95 induced tree decline and mortality. In fact, Holm oak decline may increase the response
96 of N mineralization during drying-rewetting cycles (Rodríguez et al. 2019) suggesting
97 that tree decline may exacerbate N mineralization under infrequent rains with respect to
98 wetter scenarios. The accumulation of more mobile forms of N (e.g. $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$) from the
99 increase in mineralization of N (Rodríguez et al., 2017; Avila et al., 2019; Rodríguez et
100 al., 2019) could result in net losses of N from the system because the ion nitrate is very

101 mobile and susceptible of being leached out of the system. However, to our knowledge,
102 no studies have yet explored in detail mechanisms of how drought-induced tree decline
103 (i.e., estimated using crown defoliation; see below) and mortality could affect microbial
104 N cycling-related functional groups and N cycling at larger regional scales.

105

106 In this study, we investigated the potential effects of Holm oak (*Quercus ilex* L. subsp.
107 *ballota* [Desf.] Samp) decline and mortality on soil biogeochemical cycling, soil C and N
108 mineralization and key soil functional groups (Nitrifiers and ectomycorrhizal fungi,
109 ECM) within the Spanish Iberian Peninsula. Specifically, our main aim was to understand
110 how Holm oak decline and mortality may be an agent of change that accelerates or
111 exacerbates the effects of climate change on soil biogeochemical cycling, soil C and N
112 mineralization and key soil functional groups. For this, we worked with 13 Holm oak
113 study sites distributed along the Spanish Iberian Peninsula in order to cover different
114 climatic, soil, land-use type (forests, dehesas, and open woodlands), and crown
115 defoliation (healthy, affected, and dead Holm oaks) gradients that characterize this
116 species distribution. Although Holm oak is a Mediterranean species considered to be well
117 adapted to drought conditions, it has registered important drought-related decline and
118 mortality rates in recent decades (Lloret et al., 2004; de Sampaio e Paiva Camilo-Alves
119 et al., 2013; Hereş et al., 2018). At each of our study sites, we studied soil pools. Functions
120 and functional groups related to the cycling of C, N and P and essential oligonutrient
121 content (e.g. Magnesium or Potassium). Based on previous studies, we hypothesize that:
122 i) the impact of Holm oak mortality on soil biogeochemical cycling, soil C and N
123 mineralization and key soil functional groups may obscure or even exacerbate those
124 effects from climate; ii) Holm oak mortality could alter soil N mineral forms
125 concentrations because tree mortality may affect soil key functional groups responsible

126 for the consumption (ectomycorrhizal, ECM) and generation (nitrifiers) of N mineral
127 forms.

128

129 **2. Materials and methods**

130 *2.1. Study sites and climatic data*

131 In this study we used a total of 13 Holm oak study sites, all located in the Spanish Iberian
132 Peninsula (Table 1, Fig. 1). The field study sites selection was done previously to the field
133 campaigns based on literature (Lloret et al., 2004; Corcobado et al., 2014; Camarero et
134 al., 2014; Camarero et al., 2015), different forest inventories (i.e., the third National
135 Forest Inventory, IFN3 (MAGRAMA, 2007) and the International Co-operative
136 Programme on Assessment and Monitoring of Air Pollution Effects on Forests, ICP
137 Forests (<http://icp-forests.net/>)). Site selection aimed to cover as good as possible
138 different aspects of this species distribution within the Spanish Iberian Peninsula: i). the
139 whole climatic and soil pH gradient of the distribution area; and ii). representative land-
140 use types (i.e., forests, dehesas, and open woodlands; see below) (Table 1, Fig. 1).
141 Additionally, all 13 study sites were characterized by high Holm oak decline (e.g., high
142 crown defoliation rates) and drought-induced mortality rates in recent decades (Gazol et
143 al., accepted).

144 The climate of the 13 study sites varied from oceanic (Cfb; Northern Cantabrian coast,
145 Navarra) to semiarid (BSH; Southwest Mediterranean coast, Alicante), being in most
146 cases continental Mediterranean (Csa; i.e., characterized by hot and dry summers, and
147 rainfall periods mainly concentrated in spring and autumn) according to the Köppen-
148 Geiger map on climate classification (<https://es.climate-data.org/europe/espana-5/>). The
149 mean annual temperature (MAT) of our study sites varied from 10.62 to 16.15 °C, while
150 their mean annual precipitation (MAP) varied from 326 to 919 mm (Felicísimo et al.,

151 2011) (Table 1). MAT and MAP datasets for each of our 13 study sites were obtained
152 from Felicísimo et al. (2011). This climatic datasets had a 1 km resolution grid, covered
153 a period of 57 years (from 1950 to 2007), and were built and validated using climatic data
154 from local meteorological stations (Felicísimo et al., 2011). We decided to use these
155 climatic datasets as our study sites were generally located far from any meteorological
156 station and the modelled MAT and MAP datasets from Felicísimo et al., 2011 were much
157 more precise given that they represent corrected data (i.e., considering elevation
158 gradients).

159 In order to characterize the 13 study sites depending on their land-use type we used
160 orthophotos, which allowed to quantitatively estimate the crown coverage of each of them
161 (i.e., % of trees per ha; (MAGRAMA, 2007). To do so, we used the SigPac viewer
162 (<http://signa.ign.es/signa/Pege.aspx>). Based on this approach, we considered the
163 following Holm oak land-use types: forests (hereinafter referred to as FR), study sites
164 with > 60% of crown coverage per ha; dehesas (hereinafter referred to as DH), study sites
165 with < 30% crown coverage per ha; and open woodlands (hereinafter referred to as OW),
166 study sites with 30% to 60% crown coverage per ha. In total, we considered 4 FR sites, 4
167 DH sites, and 5 OW sites for this study. The current structure of these three land-use types
168 has been traditionally determined depending on the use. Accordingly, the FR sites have
169 been historically subjected to a low human land-use intensity as they have been mainly
170 used for firewood and hunting, thus having a high crown coverage per ha. DH instead
171 have been historically subjected to an intense human land-use as they has been
172 transformed into savannah-like ecosystems, traditionally used for livestock rearing and
173 grazing, and agriculture (Pulido and Picardo, 2010). Finally, the OW sites represent
174 abandoned dehesas, meaning that they have been used in the past for livestock rearing

175 and grazing, and agriculture, but currently they are not use for such traditional activities
176 anymore.

177

178 *2.2. Experimental design and trees characterization*

179 In order to understand how soil biogeochemical cycling, microbial C and N
180 mineralization, and key soil functional groups (ECM and Nitrifiers) were affected at our
181 13 study sites by Holm oak crown defoliation and mortality, we used a factorial
182 experimental design. Within our 13 study sites, we worked with a total of 351 Holm oaks
183 (i.e., 27 trees per site) that were selected based on their crown defoliation (i.e., % of
184 foliage lost). Specifically, this crown defoliation selection was made visually, always by
185 the same observer for consistency, following Rodríguez et al. (2017) and Hereş et al.
186 (2018). At each site, one healthy reference Holm oak (i.e., with no signs of crown
187 defoliation) was identified and the selection of the 27 trees per site, based on their crown
188 defoliation, was made by comparison with this reference tree. In accordance with this
189 crown defoliation selection, at each site, we had 9 healthy (crown defoliation between 0
190 and 25%), 9 affected (crown defoliation between 25 and 99%), and 9 dead Holm oaks
191 (crown defoliation of 100%, and no visible signs of re-sprouting). In order to cover as
192 uniform as possible the area of each study site and thus to account for within site
193 heterogeneity (Medina et al. (2015)), for each of the 13 study sites we considered three
194 different subplots. These subplots were established by identifying three centroids (i.e.,
195 central points) with homogeneous environmental characteristics (i.e., slope, soil
196 exposition), around which all the needed Holm oaks have been sampled. Specifically,
197 within each subplot, we sampled 9 Holm oak trees (3 healthy, 3 affected, and 3 dead; Fig.
198 S1). The objective of this design was to randomize the error associated with potential
199 microenvironmental differences that could be associated with the crown defoliation

200 condition of our selected Holm oaks. By doing so, we minimized the effect of potential
201 confounding factors on the selected Holm oaks, and we assumed that the observed
202 variability in crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected, and dead trees) could only be
203 attributed to differences in individual tree physiological resilience responses to drought.
204 For each of the 351 Holm oaks selected for this study, we measured their height using a
205 clinometer, and their diameter at breast height (dbh) using a dbh tape. Additionally, we
206 measured two canopy diameters (i.e., the longest and the shortest) using a tape, and
207 calculated their canopy area using the ellipse area equation. In order to estimate their
208 vegetation area index (VAI), three different hemispheric photographs were taken for each
209 sampled tree at 0.5 m above the ground as close as possible to the trunk. By doing so, we
210 captured the whole surface of their crowns. The hemispheric photographs were taken
211 using a 360° fisheye lens (FCE8, Nikon) and a horizontally-levelled high resolution
212 digital camera (CoolPix 995, Nikon, Tokio, Japan) mounted on a tripod. All these
213 hemispheric photographs were further on analyzed using the Hemiview v.2.1 software
214 (Delta-T Devices Ltd, Burwell, UK) and VAI values were separately estimated for each
215 Holm oak.

216 Finally, around each of the 351 Holm oaks we visually estimated the percentage of non-
217 herbaceous (shrubs and seedlings), herbaceous, and bare soil (non-vegetation) cover.
218 Also, we counted all the trees with a dbh > 15 cm (i.e., adult trees) and with a dbh < 15
219 cm (i.e., young trees). All this aboveground cover (i.e., shrubs, seedlings, herbs, bare soil,
220 adult and young trees) was estimated within a 5-meter radio around the trunk of our Holm
221 oaks and was used to complete the characterization of our selected trees. We always
222 estimated the aboveground cover by consensus among four different observers to
223 maintain the consistency of the data.

224

225 *2.3. Soil sampling*

226 Soil samples were collected considering the three subplots that we established for each
227 of our study sites (see above). Specifically, below each of the 9 trees per subplot, we
228 extracted 3 different soil samples. We did so in order to account for the spatial
229 heterogeneity around each tree. The 3 soil samples were extracted within a radius of 50
230 cm from the trunks of the 351 Holm oaks. This was done randomly as maintaining the
231 exact same cardinal directions for all the soil samples and Holm oaks was not always
232 possible due to logistic issues (i.e., terrain characteristics such as big stones, big roots,
233 etc.). In order to extract the soil samples, we used a metallic cylinder (5 cm diameter). All
234 samples were extracted from the first 10 cm of soil after top leaf litter removal.

235 We finally had 3 composite soil samples per each of the 3 subplots of all sites.
236 Specifically, per each subplot, we mixed all the soil samples collected below the 3 healthy
237 Holm oaks in one bag, all the soil samples collected below the 3 affected Holm oaks in a
238 second bag, and all the soil samples collected below the 3 dead Holm oaks in a third bag.
239 Accordingly, we finally had 9 composite soil samples per each of the 13 study sites and
240 thus a total of 117 soil samples for the whole study.

241 Once collected, we immediately stored the soil samples in a portable fridge where a 4 °C
242 temperature was maintained until arrival to the laboratory. Then the soil within each bag
243 was homogenized. We then separated an aliquot of approx. 15 g from each of the 117 soil
244 samples and frozen it in order to preserve the natural structure of the microbial
245 communities for subsequent soil microbial diversity analysis. Finally, the remaining soil
246 samples were dried at room temperature, sieved using a 2 mm mesh size, and stored in a
247 dry dark place until further analyses.

248

249 *2.4. Soil biogeochemical variables*

250 On each of the 117 composite soil samples we collected on field (cf. previous section) we
251 carried out laboratory measurements in order to obtain information on their
252 biogeochemical characteristics. Specifically, we measured their pH considering a
253 saturated soil paste (Kalra, 1995) and using the CRISON micro pH 2001 (Hach Lange
254 Spain, S.L.U., Barcelona, SP). Then, the percentages of total carbon (C) and total nitrogen
255 (N) were obtained using an elemental analyzer (Thermo Flash 2000, Thermo Fisher
256 Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). We estimated the soil organic carbon (SOC) content as
257 the difference between the percentage of total C and the rate of inorganic C in calcium
258 carbonate (CaCO_3) (Demolon and Leroux, 1952; Allison and Moodie, 1965).
259 Additionally, we calculated the total and available phosphorus (Av P) using the method
260 described by Burriel and Hernando (1950) and an inductively coupled plasma optical
261 emission spectrometry (PerkinElmer 4300 DV, PerkinElmer Inc., Wellesley, MA, USA).
262 Specifically, this method used an extracting solution composed by CaCO_3 , MgCO_3 ,
263 H_2SO_4 and acetic acid, with a pH between 3.2 - 3.3. The cation concentration (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} ,
264 K^+ , Na^+) (M.A.P.A., 1986) of the soil samples was also calculated using an inductively
265 coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (PerkinElmer 4300 DV, PerkinElmer Inc.,
266 Wellesley, MA, USA). To determine the amount of nitrate ($\text{NO}_3^- - \text{N}$) and ammonium
267 ($\text{NH}_4^+ - \text{N}$) we used the Kjeldahl method (Kjeldahl, 1883) with a continuous flow analyzer
268 (Skalar San++, Skalar Analytical B.V., Breda, The Netherlands). Finally, all soil
269 biogeochemical variables were normalized to area (m^2) and 10 cm depth. For this, we
270 used the bulk density which was determined for each soil sample from the volume of the
271 metallic cylinder (5 cm) that we used to extract the soil samples (McKenzie et al., 2004).
272 After that, we calculated, for each soil sample, the amount found for a given soil variable
273 (e.g. nutrients) in 10 cm of depth and 1 square meter (kg SOC m^{-2} , kg Total N m^{-2} , g Av

274 P m⁻¹, g Total P m⁻¹, g Ca²⁺ m⁻¹, g Na⁺ m⁻¹, g Mg⁺ m⁻¹, mg NH₄⁺-N m⁻¹, NO₃⁻-N mg
275 m⁻¹).

276

277 *2.5. Microbial C and N mineralization*

278 Considering all 117 composite soil samples, we measured the microbial C mineralization
279 as soil heterotrophic CO₂ production (i.e., respiration; R_H). For this, we placed 40 g of
280 dry soil in a glass jar with a volume of 150 mL and rehydrated it to its 40 % water holding
281 capacity (WHC), following Lucas-Borja et al. (2016). In order to avoid potential noises
282 caused by the non-linear increases in R_H after rewetting, i.e., the so called Birch effect
283 (Birch, 1958), soils were incubated during 48 hours after rewetting while their water
284 content was kept constant. Specifically, soil samples were subjected to a temperature
285 response curve ranging from 5 to 35 °C, which roughly simulated a range of temperatures
286 that a soil could experience under Mediterranean climate. R_H was measured at each
287 increase of 10 °C (i.e., waiting between measurements until the desired temperature was
288 reached within the soil) during 60 seconds using a portable soil gas exchange system
289 (EGM-4, PP systems, MA, USA). The final R_H values represent an average of the four
290 R_H values measured for each 10 °C temperature increases (i.e., 5 °C, 15 °C, 25 °C, and 35
291 °C) at which they were measured. Besides, as a measurement of soil organic matter
292 (SOM) turnover, we also calculated the R_H per unit of organic C, hereinafter referred to
293 as “C turnover” (Curiel Yuste et al., 2007).

294 The net N mineralization was also measured as the change in time in the concentration of
295 soil mineral N (defined as the sum of NO₃⁻ - N and NH₄⁺ - N) (Jia et al., 2017).
296 Specifically, 40 g of dry soil (i.e., the same quantity we used for R_H calculations; see
297 above) were incubated following a temperature response curve that ranged from 5 to 35
298 °C and from 35 to 5 °C during 15 days. Measurements were performed every 10 °C in

299 cycles of 6 hours. The net N mineralization (R_{\min}) was calculated as the differences in
300 mineral N between day 15 and day 0 of the soil incubation period. Additionally, net
301 ammonification (R_{amm}) and nitrification (R_{nit}) were calculated as the difference in ion
302 ammonia and nitrate, respectively during the same incubation period (Jia et al., 2017).
303 Rates of soil C mineralization and soil N mineralization were normalized to area (m^2) and
304 10 cm depth ($\text{g CO}_2 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$, $\text{kg } R_{\text{amm}} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$, $\text{kg } R_{\text{nit}} \text{ day}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$, respectively),
305 following the same procedure that we described in section 2.4. (i.e., Soil biogeochemical
306 variables).

307

308 *2.6. Soil microbial biomass*

309 We measured soil microbial biomass using a modified substrate-induced respiration
310 (SIR) method (Anderson and Domsch, 1978). Specifically, this method estimates the
311 living soil microbial biomass by measuring the maximum respiratory response of the soil
312 samples after an excess of glucose is added. To do so, we placed a subsample of 10 g of
313 dry soil in a glass jar, and we rehydrated it to 40 % of its WHC. We then added 0.5 g
314 glucose kg^{-1} of dried soil and incubated it for two hours (i.e., the necessary time to have
315 an initial maximum respiratory response before any increase in microbial biomass) at 30
316 °C. After the incubation, we measured during 60s their CO_2 emissions using a portable
317 soil gas exchange system (EGM-4, PP systems, MA, USA). We did these measurements
318 for each of our 117 soil samples.

319

320 *2.7. DNA extraction, 16S and ITS amplicon sequencing*

321 From the frozen aliquot that we separated immediately after sampling to preserve the
322 natural structure of the microbial communities (cf. 2.3. Soil sampling), we extracted soil
323 DNA using the PowerSoil DNA Isolation Kit (MoBio, CA, USA) and following the

324 manufacturer's recommendations. Once extracted, we quantified the DNA using Qubit
325 3.0 (Invitrogen, CA, USA) and run an electrophoresis in a 0.8% (w/v) agarose gel stained
326 with ethidium bromide, to check its quality. After that, we sent the DNA samples to the
327 Research Technology Support Facility at the Michigan State University where the
328 construction of the amplicon libraries, according to the dual indexing strategy, was carried
329 out (Kozich et al., 2013). Specifically, for bacteria, we amplified the V4-V5 regions of
330 the 16S rRNA gene using the A515F and Y/926R primers described by (Parada et al.,
331 2016), while for fungi we targeted the ITS1 region using the ITS1FI2 and ITS2 primers
332 (Schmidt et al., 2013). We then joined each primer to their Illumina adaptor (Fluidigm
333 CS1/CS2 oligos) and barcodes, allowing for the multiplexing of the samples. After the
334 secondary PCR, we normalized each set of libraries using the Invitrogen SequelPrep
335 DNA Normalization plates (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and the
336 normalized DNA products were pooled. Once the pooled DNA was quantified and quality
337 checked, we loaded each pool on an Illumina MiSeq v2 flow cell and sequenced it with a
338 PE250 strategy using a v2 500 cycle reagent kit. Finally, we made the base calling using
339 Illumina Real Time Analysis (RTA) v1.18.54 and the output of RTA was then
340 demultiplexed and converted to the FastQ format with Illumina Bcl2fastq v2.18.0.

341

342 *2.8. Bioinformatic analyses of sequenced data*

343 We pre-processed the FastQ files (cf. 2.7. DNA extraction, 16S and ITS amplicon
344 sequencing) using the software FastQC (Andrews, 2010) by taking into account the
345 quality of the sequences and removing Illumina adapters if present. After this first step,
346 we assembled the reads using the pandaseq tool (Bartram et al., 2011) and setting the
347 overlapping parameters by using a 0.9 threshold quality for alignment and removing the
348 primers. Once we had the reads overlapped, we processed the sequences with Qiime 1.9.1

349 (Caporaso et al., 2010), which identifies and removes chimeras through USEARCH 6.1
350 by using the RDP gold database for bacteria and the UNITE chimera database for fungi.
351 We clustered the resulting sequences into operational taxonomic units (OTUs) with an
352 open-reference OTU picking process (pick_open_reference_otus from Qiime 1.9.1) at a
353 97 % sequence identity to taxonomically assign the representative sequences for each
354 OTU. For this, we used the RDP classifier database (Cole et al., 2014), with a threshold
355 of 0.8, as a reference. The process of clustering the fungal ITS sequences was similar to
356 that used for bacteria but, in this case, the taxonomic identification of representative
357 OTUs was made using the UNITE database as a reference. Once we had the biom file,
358 we further carried out our analysis in R v. 3.5.1 (R Core Team, 2016) using the phyloseq
359 v. 1.24.2 (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013) and vegan v. 2.5-4 (Oksanen et al., 2019)
360 packages.

361 Overall, we targeted the functional groups directly associated with key paths of soil N
362 cycling. Specifically, from the whole prokaryote and fungal communities we targeted the
363 following functional groups: ectomycorrhiza, which are specialized in improving the
364 capacity of plants to uptake the soil mineral N; and Nitrifiers, responsible for the
365 transformation of the ammonia ion (NH_4^+ - N) into nitrate (NO_3^- - N) (nitrification). For
366 this, we used FUNGuild (Nguyen et al., 2016), a tool that compares the taxonomic
367 identification of the fungal community with a known database, and assigns fungal guilds
368 to all obtained fungal sequences. Specifically, we extracted all fungal sequences assigned
369 to the ectomycorrhizal (ECM) guild. We also selected several orders of the archaea
370 [*Nitrososphaerales* (Kerou et al., 2018)], bacteria [*Nitrosomonadales*, (Wang and Chen,
371 2018), and *Nitrospirales* (Spieck and Bock, 2015)] kingdoms involved in the process of
372 nitrification, and created a functional group that integrated them all (hereinafter referred

373 to as Nitrifiers). Finally, we calculated the relative abundance of the ectomycorrhizal
374 fungi and of the Nitrifiers in the available 117 composite soil samples.

375

376 *2.9. Statistical analyses*

377 For all the variables that we used in our statistical analyses we first performed normality
378 tests and log (e.g., SOC, total N, total P, NO_3^- - N, Ca^{2+} , microbial biomass, R_{nit} , R_{H} , C
379 turnover) or square root (e.g., ECM, Nitrifiers) transformed them when the normal
380 distribution assumption was not met.

381 We tested for differences in tree-related variables (i.e., see Table S1 for their complete
382 list), aboveground cover (i.e., see Table S1 for their complete list), abiotic factors and
383 percentage of crown coverage per ha (i.e., MAT, MAP, pH, and % Cc; see Table S3), and
384 soil biogeochemical variables (i.e., see Table S4 for their complete list) between the
385 different land-use types (i.e., FR, DH, and OW) by performing one-way ANOVA
386 analyses followed by a Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) post hoc test.
387 Crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected, and dead Holm oak trees) comparisons between
388 different land-use types have been also tested based on one-way ANOVA analyses
389 followed by a Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) post hoc test.

390 We evaluated the effects of abiotic factors (i.e., MAT, MAP, and pH), land-use type, and
391 crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected, and dead Holm oaks), as well as their
392 interactions (i.e., the fixed part of the model) on all soil biogeochemical variables (i.e.,
393 see Table 2 for their complete list) and on all soil functional variables (i.e., see Table 3
394 for their complete list) by running separate Linear Mixed-Effects models (LME) for each
395 of them (Pinheiro et al., 2017). To run all these LMEs, we created a Boolean variable
396 called "livestock grazing", which indicated the presence or absence of livestock at our
397 study sites. This was done to control for possible effects caused by grazing animals since

398 the DH land-use type is usually used for livestock, while the FR and OW land-use types
399 are not or not anymore (Pulido and Picardo, 2010). This Boolean variable was introduced
400 in the LMEs as nested within study sites and with a random effect. To control for data
401 duplicity, we first checked the co-variance and multicollinearity of the fixed factors using
402 the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and eliminated from further analyses all those that
403 had VIF values higher than 2 (Zuur et al., 2010). Finally, we selected the models that
404 showed the lowest AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) values in each case as being the
405 best suited ones.

406 In order to see how our different soil biogeochemical and functional variables may be
407 grouped into two linear axes that would explain the maximum amount of variance, a
408 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed (Fig. 2). Specifically, we first
409 removed the effects of the abiotic factors (i.e., MAT, MAP, and pH) and land-use type
410 on soil biogeochemical and functional variables through the LMEs explained within the
411 previous paragraph. Then, we used the residuals of the LMEs to run PCA by accounting
412 for crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected, and dead Holm oaks). We further used the
413 results of the LMEs to build and run a Structural Equation Model (SEM). For this, we
414 used the “psem” function available from the piecewiseSEM package (Lefcheck, 2016), a
415 function that allowed to introduce random effects (i.e., similar to the structure we used
416 for LMEs). Specifically, we introduced into SEM the following explicative variables:
417 abiotic factors (i.e., MAT, MAP, and pH) and crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected,
418 and dead Holm oaks). Our purpose was to look for all potential causal-effect relationships
419 between the explicative variables and all measured soil variables: biogeochemical,
420 cycling, microbial C and N mineralization, and functional groups (ECM and Nitrifiers).
421 To test the goodness of fit of our SEM, we calculated the Fisher’s C statistic, which
422 follows a chi-squared distribution and tests if the model fits the data ($p > 0.05$) or not (p

423 < 0.05). Finally, we completed our final SEM selection based on the AIC coefficient
424 (Lefcheck, 2016).

425 We carried out all statistical analyses in R v. 3.5.1 (R Core Team, 2016). Relationships
426 for all our statistical analyses were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

427

428 **3. Results**

429 *3.1. Aboveground cover structure as a function of land-use type and crown defoliation*

430 Aboveground site structure, estimated around each of our 351 Holm oaks, varied across
431 the different land-use types (i.e., FR, DH, and OW) and the different crown defoliation
432 levels (i.e., healthy, affected, and dead trees) (Tables S1 and S2). Specifically, the DH
433 land-use type had a significantly higher herbaceous cover than FR and OW. The DH land-
434 use type had also trees with larger canopies and dbh than the FR and OW land-use types
435 (Table S1). Trees in OW were the smallest in height of all land-uses. Vegetation area
436 index (VAI) and the total number of trees around the selected Holm oaks were
437 significantly lower in DH compared to FR and OW. It was also observed a significant
438 decrease in VAI with tree crown defoliation and dead under OW and DH, but not under
439 FR (Table S2). The percentage of surface covered by bare soil under DH increased
440 significantly with tree crown defoliation and dead (Table S2). ANOVA and subsequent
441 post hoc analyses further shows that sites belonging to the DH land-use type were on
442 average warmer (higher MAT), wetter (MAP) and more acidic (lower pH) than the two
443 other land-use types (Table S3)

444

445 *3.2. Variability in soil biogeochemical variables, microbial C and N mineralization and*
446 *functional groups associated with differences in land-use type, abiotic variables and*
447 *crown defoliation*

448 According to the results from the LMEs, the abiotic factors (i.e., MAT, MAP, and pH)
449 and crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected, and dead) were the main explanatory
450 variables that showed additive and interactive effects over our analyzed soil variables
451 (Tables 2 and 3). Still, only total N showed a positive relation with land-use type (FR,
452 DH, and OW) (Tables 2 and 3), while the rest of the variables were especially sensitive
453 to MAP variability rather than to MAT variability (Tables 2 and 3). Specifically, MAP
454 affected positively SOC and R_{amm} , and negatively the pools of mineral N and the Nitrifiers
455 (Tables 2 and 3). On the other hand, soil pH affected the capacity of soils to oxidize
456 ammonium by controlling the amount of soil available NH_4^+ - N (i.e. a decrease in pH
457 resulted in the liberation of NH_4^+ - N, see Table 3) further affecting net nitrification rates
458 (R_{nit}). Furthermore, soil pH was positively correlated with soil microbial biomass and R_H
459 (Table 3).

460

461 Overall, crown defoliation was the factor that was best correlated with soil pools, soil C
462 and N mineralization and relative abundances of functional groups (Tables 2 and 3; Figs.
463 2, and 3). For instance, SOC was positively affected by both MAP and crown defoliation.
464 Moreover, crown defoliation and subsequent death was related to a decrease in soil C
465 turnover (R_H per unit of SOC), resulting also in a net decrease in rates of mineralization
466 of N (hence crown defoliation affected negatively both R_H and R_{amm} ; Figs. 2 and 3).
467 Crown defoliation was also strongly associated with the accumulation of Av and total P
468 but also with net losses of essential ions such as Mg^{2+} and Na^+ (Table 2). Overall, we
469 observed an especially strong influence of crown defoliation over pools, soil metabolic
470 paths and functional guilds strongly associated with the N cycle (Table 3, Fig. 3). Crown
471 defoliation was associated with large changes in the ectomycorrhizal (decrease) and
472 Nitrifiers (increase) communities resulting in a net increase on R_{nit} (Fig. 3) and in

473 accumulation of the ion nitrate ($\text{NO}_3^- - \text{N}$) under dead trees in detriment of the ion
474 ammonium ($\text{NH}_4^+ - \text{N}$) (Table 2, Fig. 3). This alterations further lead to a net
475 accumulation of the most mobile forms of N ($\text{NO}_3^- - \text{N}$) and P (available P) related to the
476 observed increase with crown defoliation of the relative abundance of Nitrifiers and the
477 decrease of ectomycorrhizal fungi (Table 3; Figs. 2 and 3). Moreover, our results show
478 also how Nitrifiers play an important role by being associated with the decrease in
479 ammonium ($\text{NH}_4^+ - \text{N}$) concentration and the decrease in R_{nit} (Fig. 3).

480

481 **4. Discussion**

482 Our study provides solid evidences on strong drought-induced tree mortality effects over
483 soil biogeochemical cycling, rates of microbial C and N mineralization, and relative
484 abundances of key functional groups (ECM and Nitrifiers), which in many cases obscured
485 and/or exacerbated the direct effects of the wide Peninsular climatic gradient of this study.
486 These results are of great importance in the current context, in which, the increase in the
487 frequency of severe droughts episodes is causing the increase in the frequency of episodes
488 of drought-induced tree mortality (Allen et al., 2010; Allen et al., 2015; Hartmann et al.,
489 2018). Our results indicate that drought-induced tree mortality could potentially
490 aggravate the expected negative effects of climate over soil biogeochemical cycling,
491 microbial C and N mineralization, and key functional groups. However, accounting for
492 this phenomenon in predictions requires taking into account some of the complex
493 interactions and the exchanges of energy and matter occurring between plants and soil,
494 interactions that stat-of-the-art soil models, e.g. RothC (Lenkinson and Rayner, 2006),
495 CENTURY (Parton et al., 1987; Paustian et al., 1992) or Yasso (Liski et al., 2005, Tuomi
496 et al., 2011) are currently not taking into account. This reductionist approach could be a
497 potential reason for the difficulties in correctly simulating the impacts of climate extremes

498 on biogeochemical cycling, forest stability and subsequent climate feedbacks (Reichstein
499 et al., 2013; Bahn et al., 2014).

500

501 In the climatic gradient covered in this study, the latitudinal decrease in precipitation
502 (MAP) played a relevant role by limiting the accumulation of soil C, as well as limiting
503 key soil functions involved in the N and C cycling, such as the net N ammonification
504 (R_{amm}) and heterotrophic respiration (R_H), respectively. This is not surprising, since it is
505 well known that microbial activity is very sensitive to changes in water availability (e.g.
506 Curiel Yuste et al. 2007, 2011, Sardans et al 2005,2006). Indeed, our precipitation
507 gradient shows how water limits the capacity of soil microbiota to decompose SOM,
508 hence altering R_H (Curiel Yuste et al., 2003; Curiel Yuste et al., 2007; Moyano et al.,
509 2012; Sardans and Peñuelas, 2013; Jiao et al., 2016; Jeong et al., 2018) as well as other
510 functions related to N mineralization (Chen et al., 2011; Larsen et al., 2011; Xu et al.,
511 2016).

512

513 However, we found that Holm oak crown defoliation and subsequent death triggered a
514 cascade of causal-effect processes that exacerbated the potential and well documented
515 effects of drought over soil biogeochemical variables, microbial C and N mineralization,
516 and functional groups (ECM and Nitrifiers). These evidences, therefore, point to drought-
517 induced tree decline and mortality as a highly important factor that should be taken into
518 account in order to understand how ongoing changes in local climate could potentially
519 affect soil C and nutrient cycling ((Gómez-Aparicio et al., 2017; Bastida et al., 2019;
520 Curiel Yuste et al., 2019). For instance, crown defoliation was, together with precipitation
521 (MAP), the only variable that explained most of the observed changes in SOC
522 sequestration. Accumulation of senescent leaves and fine roots (Curiel Yuste et al., 2019)

523 together with the observed decrease in C turnover rates (R_H on a C basis) following the
524 reduction in labile C inputs that stimulate R_H (e.g. root exudates; see Kuzyakov (2002);
525 Blagodatskaya and Kuzyakov (2008)) could explain this increase in SOC associated with
526 crown defoliation. Crown defoliation was also related to further stoichiometric
527 imbalances, resulting from alterations in soil nutrient concentrations, e.g. losses of
528 essential oligonutrients (Mg^{2+} and Na^+) and the transformation of other nutrients into
529 mobile forms (NO_3^- - N and Av P) that are being accumulated in soil and not taken up by
530 plants. These stoichiometric imbalances could further hinder the recovery (e.g., Holm oak
531 regeneration) of these highly human-transformed ecosystems because, e.g. non-uptaken
532 mobile forms of N and P could be easily leached out of the systems (e.g. Koskinen et al.
533 2011) and Mg^{2+} is an essential constituent of the rubisco enzyme. Hence, this nutrient
534 lossess and soil stoichiometry imbalances from tree mortality could hasten the conversion
535 of these woodlands into shrublands or grasslands (Fensham et al., 2009; Anderegg et al.,
536 2012) further affecting the C and nutrient source/sink dynamics (Adams et al., 2010;
537 Hicke et al., 2012). Particularly, the observed lack of recruitment (% of non-herbaceous
538 vegetation) and the decrease of the vegetation area index (VAI) after tree mortality,
539 observed under more intensively managed sites (OW and DH), support this idea and
540 suggest that the capacity of these ecosystems to recover after tree mortality events could
541 be compromised.

542

543 Tree mortality effects were especially intense over the metabolic paths involving soil N
544 cycling, obscuring in many cases the well-known sensitivity to drought of key N
545 processes such as nitrification (Chen et al., 2011). This is consistent with previous results
546 showing how severely the N cycle could be affected by the loss of tree health and its
547 subsequent mortality (Jenkins et al., 1999; Griffin et al., 2011; Xiong et al., 2011; Edburg

548 et al., 2012; Avila et al., 2016; Rodríguez et al., 2017). The structural equation model
549 (SEM) showed imbalances in the production/consumption of mineral forms of N (ion
550 ammonia and nitrate) mediated to a large extent by the change in the relative abundance
551 of key microbial functional groups involved in N cycling. Tree mortality resulted in
552 accumulation of mobile forms of N (NO_3^- - N) due to the stimulation of the transformation
553 of NH_4^+ - N into NO_3^- - N (R_{nit}). This increase in the soil concentration of the most mobile
554 form of N, NO_3^- - N associated with crown defoliation and death was positively associated
555 with the proliferation of Nitrifiers and the decrease in the ectomycorrhizal fungi (ECM),
556 which are responsible for the uptake of soil N for plant consumption (Koide et al., 2014).
557 Accumulation of the most mobile form of N, NO_3^- - N, therefore, resulted from the
558 increase in the nitrification process but from the decrease in its consumption by
559 vegetation, evidenced by the disruption of the symbiotic plant-fungus relationship (ECM)
560 as tree health declined. While this observed increase in the production of NO_3^- - N by the
561 soil microbiota following tree mortality has not been identified before, it was, according
562 to our SEM, further facilitated by the parallel increase in available P (Av P), which
563 generally becomes a limiting nutrient under no limitation of N (He and Dijkstra, 2015;
564 Deng et al., 2017). Hence, net increases in mobile forms of essential nutrient during tree
565 decline and mortality could easily result in net losses of these essential losses from the
566 system. For instance, the accumulation of mobile forms of N (NO_3^- - N) associated with
567 tree mortality may stimulate denitrification processes and lead to emissions of N oxides
568 (e.g. N_2O) to the atmosphere (Li et al., 2016). Nitrate accumulation, together with mobile
569 forms of P (i.e., Av P), might also lead to losses of N and P through leaching to aquifers
570 or other water sources, which could potentially alter water quality (e.g., eutrophication)
571 as well as deteriorate soils, and further accelerating the process of conversion into
572 shrublands or grasslands (Stark and Richards, 2008).

573

574 **5. Conclusions**

575 We conclude that an in-depth understanding of how drought-induced tree decline and
576 mortality alters the plant-soil relationships are needed in order to better understand
577 climate-change effects on soil C and nutrient cycling. In fact, direct alterations resulting
578 from the changes in climate in this large Peninsular climatic gradient were, in many cases,
579 obscured and/or exacerbated by the effect of tree crown defoliation and mortality. Holm
580 oak crown defoliation and mortality trigger a cascade of causal-effect relationships
581 leading to important changes in the relative abundance of key soil microbial functional
582 groups such as Nitrifiers and ectomycorrhizal fungi (ECM) that resulted in important
583 transformations of some of the metabolic pathways controlling N and P cycling. Negative
584 consequences of the subsequent accumulation of mobile forms of N (NO_3^- - N) or P (Av
585 P) associated with tree mortality might be multiple: stimulate denitrification leading to
586 emissions of N oxides (e.g. N_2O) to the atmosphere; leaching of these mobile forms of N
587 and P to aquifers or other water sources, which could potentially alter water quality (e.g.,
588 eutrophication) as well as deteriorate soils; or accelerating the process of conversion into
589 shrublands or grasslands. Integrating into models knowledge on the mechanisms that
590 relate tree mortality with key metabolic pathways controlling the cycling of C, N and P
591 and other essential oligonutrients (e.g. Mg^{2+}) might be needed to improve our predictions
592 of climate change effects on soil biogeochemical cycling, microbial C and N
593 mineralization, and key soil functional groups (ECM and Nitrifiers).

594

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608

609 **Data Availability**

610 The datasets analyzed in this study are available in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive
611 (SRA) repository (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra) under the BioProject accession number
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901 **Fig. captions**

902

903 **Fig. 1.** Holm oak distribution within the Spanish Iberian Peninsula and the location of the
904 13 study sites (small capture; bottom right hand situated map). The numbers on the map
905 correspond to the study sites mentioned in Table 1. The big capture illustrates the
906 sampling design with the 3 subplots that were selected for each of our study sites and the
907 healthy (squares), affected (triangles), and dead (circles) Holm oaks that have been
908 selected and sampled (see Materials and methods for details). This latter capture
909 illustrates only one of the 13 sites, as an example, but it is representative for all of them.

910

911 **Fig. 2.** Principal Component Analysis (PCA) results showing how soil biogeochemical
912 and functional variables may be grouped into two linear axes as a function of crown
913 defoliation. Square symbols represent healthy Holm oaks, triangle ones represent affected
914 Holm oaks, and circle ones represent dead Holm oaks. *Where*, C turnover = R_H per unit
915 of SOC; R_H = heterotrophic respiration; ECM = ectomycorrhizal fungi; R_{amm} = net
916 ammonification; NH_4^+ - N = soil ammonium content; Ca^{2+} = calcium; Na^+ = sodium;
917 Mg^+ = magnesium; Total N = total nitrogen; Total P = total *phosphorus*; SOC = soil
918 organic carbon; Av P = available phosphorus; R_{nit} = net nitrification; NO_3^- - N = soil
919 nitrate content.

920

921 **Fig. 3.** Structural Equation Model (SEM) results. The path diagram represents
922 hypothesized causal relationships between abiotic factors (i.e., MAT, MAP, and pH),
923 crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected, and dead Holm oaks), and soil biogeochemical
924 variables, microbial C and N mineralization, and functional groups. Causal relationships
925 are indicated by arrows as it follows: positive and negative effects are indicated by solid

926 and dashed lines respectively, and numbers indicate the standardized estimated
927 regressions weights (SRW). Black arrows represent significant relationships, while grey
928 arrows represent marginally significant relationships. *Where*, MAT = mean annual
929 temperature; MAP = mean annual precipitation; R_H = heterotrophic respiration; Av P =
930 available phosphorus; SOC = soil organic carbon; R_{amm} = net ammonification; $NH_4^+ - N$
931 = soil ammonium content; R_{nit} = net nitrification; $NO_3^- - N$ = soil nitrate content; ECM =
932 ectomycorrhizal fungi.

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936 Fig. 2

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942 **Table 1.** Site description including: land-use type (FR, forests; DH, dehesas; OW, open
 943 woodland), geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude), elevation, percentage of
 944 crown coverage (Cc) per ha, abiotic factors (MAT, mean annual temperature; MAP, mean
 945 annual precipitation; and pH).

Study sites (number)	Land-use type	Latitude	Longitude	Elevatio n (m)	% Cc (ha ⁻¹)	MAT (°C)	MAP (mm)	Soil pH
Huelva (1)	DH	37.9820	-6.5125	405	16	16.15	892	5.89
Tres Cantos (2)	DH	40.6714	-3.6827	806	15	12.86	591	5.54
Chapinería (3)	DH	40.3833	-4.1938	649	27	12.88	601	6.35
Plasencia (4)	DH	39.8775	-6.0490	367	10	15.37	740	5.38
Talavera de la Reina (5)	OW	39.7846	-5.0742	427	47	15.41	559	5.87
Sevilla (6)	OW	37.9727	-6.0193	729	45	15.15	637	6.04
Pamplona (7)	OW	42.7323	-1.7504	624	48	10.62	919	7.33
Formiche Bajo (8)	OW	40.2974	-0.8727	1044	43	13.08	497	7.78
Granada (9)	OW	37.5012	-2.5042	1221	42	12.41	326	7.03
Lleida (10)	FR	41.8304	1.4516	609	63	13.08	569	7.19
Ciudad Real (11)	FR	38.5056	-3.2480	814	85	14.52	484	6.29
Guadalajara (12)	FR	40.8753	-3.1626	889	84	12.10	573	4.86
Alcoy (13)	FR	38.6659	-0.5395	1014	90	13.83	519	7.52

946 *Where, numbers in brackets from column Study sites (number) represent the numbers that have been used*
 947 *in Fig. 1 to identify the 13 study sites; pH, mean pH values of all soil samples extracted from each study*
 948 *site*

949 **Table 2.** Results of Linear Mixed-Effects models (LMEs): effects of abiotic factors (i.e.,
950 MAT, MAP, and pH), land-use type, and crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected, and
951 dead Holm oaks), as well as their interactions (i.e., the fixed part of the model) on all soil
952 biogeochemical variables. p – values marked in bold indicate significant or marginally
953 significant relationships.

Response variables	Estimate	SE	df	t-value	p-value
SOC *					
MAP	0.001	<0.001	101	1.978	0.05
Crown defoliation	0.004	0.002	101	2.089	0.04
MAP x Crown defoliation	-0.001	<0.001	101	-1.704	0.09
Total N *					
land-use type	-0.011	0.003	11	-3.119	0.01
Crown defoliation	<0.001	<0.001	103	1.483	0.14
Total P *					
MAT	0.244	0.093	10	2.631	0.025
land-use type	-0.009	0.005	10	-1.683	0.123
Crown defoliation	0.001	<0.001	94	2.809	0.006
NH₄⁺ - N					
MAT	-86.006	39.269	11	-2.190	0.05
MAP	-1.472	0.667	96	-2.206	0.03
Crown defoliation	-6.712	3.434	96	-1.957	0.05
MAT x MAP	0.128	0.05	96	2.511	0.01
MAT x Crown defoliation	0.517	0.262	96	1.975	0.05
MAP x Crown defoliation	0.01	0.005	96	2.181	0.03
MAT x MAP x Crown defoliation	-0.001	<0.001	96	-2.224	0.03
NO₃⁻ - N *					
MAT	0.098	0.117	11	0.840	0.42
MAP	-0.002	0.001	102	-1.571	0.12

	Crown defoliation	0.005	0.001	102	3.790	<0.001
	Av P					
	Crown defoliation	<0.001	<0.001	101	2.387	0.02
	Ca²⁺ *					
	pH	0.467	0.043	100	10.951	<0.001
	Na⁺					
	Crown defoliation	-0.001	<0.001	102	-1.983	0.05
	Mg⁺					
	Crown defoliation	-0.014	0.005	103	-2.832	0.0056

954 *Where*, SE = standard error; MAP = mean annual precipitation; MAT = mean annual temperature; SOC =
955 soil organic carbon; Total N = total nitrogen; Total P = total *phosphorus*; NH₄⁺ - N = soil ammonium
956 content; NO₃⁻ - N = soil nitrate content; Av P = available phosphorus; Ca²⁺ = calcium; Na⁺ = sodium; Mg⁺
957 = magnesium. Variables marked with * have been log transformed.

958 **Table 3.** Results of Linear Mixed-Effects models (LMEs): effects of abiotic factors (i.e.,
959 MAT, MAP, and pH), land-use type, and crown defoliation (i.e., healthy, affected, and
960 dead Holm oaks), as well as their interactions (i.e., the fixed part of the model) on all soil
961 functional variables. p – values marked in bold indicate significant or marginally
962 significant relationships.

Response variables	Estimate	SE	df	t-value	p-value
Microbial biomass *					
pH	0.263	0.057	103	4.61	<0.001
Nitrifiers **					
MAP	-0.001	0.000	94	-2.160	0.03
Crown defoliation	0.001	0.001	94	3.752	<0.001
ECM **					
Crown defoliation	-0.013	0.003	99	-4.280	<0.001
R_{amm}					
MAP	0.027	0.012	100	2.312	0.02
Crown defoliation	-0.041	0.011	100	-3.615	<0.001
R_{nit} *					
pH	0.264	0.127	97	2.081	0.04
Crown defoliation	0.005	0.001	97	3.246	0.002
R_H *					
pH	0.537	0.068	101	7.900	<0.001
Crown defoliation	-0.001	<0.001	101	-2.012	0.05
C turnover *					
pH	0.510	0.073	99	7.01	<0.001
Crown defoliation	-0.001	0.000	99	-2.368	0.02

963 *Where, SE = standard error; MAP = mean annual precipitation; ECM = ectomycorrhizal fungi; R_{amm} = net*
964 *ammonification; R_{nit} = net nitrification; R_H = heterotrophic respiration; C turnover = R_H per unit of SOC.*
965 *Variables marked with * have been log transformed, while variables marked with ** have been square root*
966 *transformed.*

